

Challenges of E-Commerce in India

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Abstract

Electronic Commerce is the process of doing business through computer networks. A person sitting on his chair in front of a computer can access all the facilities of the Internet to buy or sell the products. Unlike traditional commerce that is carried out physically with the effort of a person to go & get products, e-commerce has made it easier for the human to reduce physical work and to save time. E-Commerce which was started in the early 1990's has taken a great leap in the world of computers, but the fact that has hindered the growth of e-commerce is security. Security is the challenge facing e-commerce today & there is still a lot of advancement made in the field of security. The main advantage of e-commerce over traditional commerce is the user can browse online shops, compare prices and order merchandise sitting at home on their PC. The research strategy shows the importance of the e-commerce in developing countries for business applications.

Meaning

Electronic commerce, or e-commerce, (also written as e-commerce) is a type of business model, or segment of a larger business model, that enables a firm or individual to conduct business over an electronic network, typically the internet. Electronic commerce operates in all four of the major market segments: business to business, business to consumer, consumer to consumer, and consumer to business. It can be thought of as a more advanced form of mail-order purchasing through a catalog. Almost any product or service can be offered via e-commerce, from books and music to financial services and plane tickets.

Definition of E-Commerce

Electronic commerce or e-commerce is a term for any type of business, or commercial transaction, that involves the transfer of information across the Internet. It covers a range of different types of businesses, from consumer based retail sites, through auction or music sites, to business exchanges trading goods and services between corporations. It is currently one of the most important aspects of the Internet to emerge.

Objectives of E-Commerce

High Reach Ability: The main objective and at the same time need is traction on your web store. Of, course if you are selling

products online what you require are customers. If you are getting good reach ability, then your business will grow. Therefore one of the objectives is high reach ability.

High Conversions: If people are coming on your web store and purchasing something then it will calculate as conversions and from the number of people who are buying stuff from your web store we can calculate the conversion rate.

Customer Satisfaction: Customer is the main part of any E-commerce business, so it's very important to make your customer happy and satisfied. By providing quality and desirable products, on time delivery, 24*7 customer support, and timely sale & best deal offers you can make your customer happy. It is one of the main objectives of E-commerce.

Social Popularity: Unless and until you are not famous and popular among people you cannot establish your brand. Social presence with Omni channel & Digital marketing is essential for any E-commerce business.

Scope of E-Commerce Business

- Another significant contributor to the growth of E-Commerce in India in the future is the e-tailing industry which largely deals in providing jewelry, apparel and kitchen appliances online.
- Websites like Flipkart, Myntra, Amazon, Snapdeal, Jabong, etc. are all examples of the enormous success of E-Commerce in India. Due to these firms, India is one of the fastest growing E-Commerce markets in Asia/Pacific with China investing as much. Many analysts believe that the advent of 3G/4G speed in net connectivity has been a major cog in the wheel for such a growth in this market.
- As India has been the heart of the e-commerce market in 2016 with the tremendous growth of 70%. The consumer base is expected to hit 100 million in 2017, and this ensures that any e-commerce venture would soon be the best business in India, as far as profits and growth are concerned.

Challenges of E-Commerce Business in India

Despite huge opportunity in the E-Commerce business, E-Commerce business presents several particular challenges which are sometimes difficult to handle for any new startup. However, without any doubt, India has been a profitable E-Commerce market from the last seven years in a row.

Thus many venture capitalists, angel investors, private companies & high-net-worth individuals are investing money in E-Commerce, no matter how small or big the business. E-commerce is growing rapidly, but it is still facing several hurdles in operations in India.

Internet Issues: The Internet is mandatory is the foundation of E-Commerce. However, in India internet penetration is still low at 34.8 percent of the population. However, due to the growth of the mobile internet, India is witnessing an exception increase in the year 2015 and 2016, allowing E-Commerce businesses to reach to masses easily.

Branding & Marketing: To drive sales and traffic on an E-Commerce site involves a heavy budget for branding and marketing. This cost is significant and can be calculated as cost per acquisition or cost per sale. As per marketing guru's the current average CPA for the E-Commerce business is between INR 500–1000, which isn't practically sustainable for small startups having less to invest in such high volume marketing campaign.

However, concept or niche E-Commerce business can drive sales in very low CPA because the customer is limited for such category of products.

Declining Margins: With the entry of several players already in Indian E-Commerce market, the customer is pampered by offering big discounts, offers, deals and easy return options etc.

resulting in low margins. For example in financial, the year 2013, major E-Commerce players had posted revenue of Rs 1,195.9 crore and loss of Rs 344.6 crore. But for Flipkart, making losses was a conscious decision.

In an interview with Business Standard, Flipkart promoters said that “Profitability is not a focus area for them and they are still looking to acquire more market shares.

Logistics & Delivery: Delivering product to buyers is still a major hurdle for any new E-Commerce startup. Keeping in mind that E-Commerce logistics is different from traditional deliveries of goods because there are no middle-men involved in the final delivery of the product on customers’ doorstep.

The critical element in an E-Commerce logistics is the last mile delivery of the product to the customer. Several E-Commerce startups’ failed because of their last mile delivery capability. You can either own or outsource the E-Commerce logistics service.

Tax-Related Issues: Taxation is another big hurdle in India for any startup and its a major factor for less growth rate of E-Commerce in India as compared to developed countries like USA and UK. In those countries, tax slabs are uniform for all sectors whereas tax structure of India varies from product to product and region to region.

This factor creates accounting problems for any E-Commerce business because E-Commerce is not limited to product categories or regions.

Touch and Feel: Indian customers’ mindset is more traditional and people are more comfortable buying products from physical stores rather than E-Commerce stores. E-Commerce companies selling products like apparel, handicrafts, jewelry have to face challenges to sell their products as the buyers want to see, touch and feel before they make the buying decision.

Advantages of E-Commerce

- Low Financial Cost
- Potential Income
- Sell Internationally
- Easy to Showcase Bestsellers
- Personalized Online Experience
- Affordable employees
- Easier to Encourage Impulse Buy
- Easy to Retarget or Remarket to Customer
- Customers Get a Less Invasive Experience
- Gain Access to Customer Data Easily
- Able to Process a High Number of Orders
- Can Scale Business Quickly
- Can Grow Business Organically with Content

Disadvantage of E-Commerce

- No One Can Buy During a Site Crash
- Customers Can’t Try Before They Buy
- E-commerce Is Highly Competitive
- Customers Can Be Impatient
- You Need To Ship Your Products
- Physical Retail is Still More Popular Despite Decline.

Top 10 Popular E-Commerce Sites Indians Like to Shop at

- Amazon India
- Flipkart
- Alibaba
- eBay India
- Jabong
- Shop clues

Types of E-Commerce Business Models

The first thing that comes to our mind when we talk about E-Commerce is that it is an online commercial or sales transaction that takes place between the supplier and the customer. While the idea of the concept is right, there are more specific factors involved that categorize E-Commerce into six major types. Each of these types has different features and attributes.

- Business-to-Business (B2B)
- Business-to-Consumer (B2C)
- Consumer-to-Consumer (C2C)
- Consumer-to-Business (C2B)
- Business-to-Administration (B2A)
- Consumer-to-Administration (C2A)

Working of E-Commerce

The consumer moves through the internet to the merchant's web site. From there, he decides that he wants to purchase something, so he is moved to the online transaction server, where all of the information he gives is encrypted. Once he has placed his order, the information moves through a private gateway to a Processing Network, where the issuing and acquiring banks complete or deny the transaction. This generally takes place in no more than 5-7seconds.

There are many different payment systems available to accommodate the varied processing needs of merchants, from those who have a few orders a day to those who process thousands of transactions daily. With the addition of Secure Layer Technology, E-Commerce is also a very safe way to complete transactions.

Conclusion

E-Commerce refers to all forms of business activities across the internet. This can include E-tailing, intranets and extranets, present challenges in E-commerce and simply online presence of any form that are used for some type of communication. E-Commerce has several advantages and disadvantages as indicated in these papers.

E-Commerce applications that started in the early 1970's need to be still developed regarding security and efficiency. For the developing country like our India advancement in E-commerce is a challenge to compete with the developed countries.

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